

Figure S1. Daily average maximum and minimum temperatures during the experimental period.

Table S1. Ingredient composition of diets fed to cows during the late lactation (lactating diet), far-off period (far-off diet), close-up period (close-up diet) and early lactation (fresh diet).

Ingredient (% of DM)	Lactating	Far-off	Close-up	Fresh
Corn silage	42.94	23.97	29.97	34.76
Wheat straw	---	18.44	11.99	---
Bermudagrass hay	6.83	22.12	19.98	11.30
Brewers grains, wet	14.64	10.14	5.99	10.43
SoyChlor ¹	---	---	9.99	---
Liquid supplement ²	3.42	---	4.00	4.78
Ground Corn	7.81	8.29	9.99	9.99
Urea	0.20	0.55	---	0.09
Corn gluten feed	1.95	3.69	---	5.21
Citrus pulp	3.51	---	---	6.51
Cottonseed meal	4.39	3.69	---	---
Soybean hulls, pelleted	4.88	3.69	1.99	3.04
Soybean meal	2.93	1.84	1.99	4.34
Amino plus ³	---	---	---	2.17
Prolak ⁴	2.44	---	---	3.04
Salt, white	0.39	0.37	0.20	0.26
Calcium carbonate	0.98	---	0.40	0.87
Sodium sesquinate refined	0.88	---	---	0.87
Magnesium oxide	0.39	0.26	---	0.43
DCAD plus ⁵	0.49	---	---	0.35
OmniGen-AF ⁶	0.23	0.44	0.48	---
Rumensin ⁷	0.25	0.29	0.43	0.24
Procreatin ⁸	---	---	---	---
ClariFly ⁹	---	0.05	0.08	---
Diamond V XP ¹⁰	---	0.42	0.45	---
ReaShure Choline ¹¹	---	---	0.49	---
Smartamine M ¹²	---	---	0.06	---
Prequel [VIRTUS] ¹³	---	---	0.78	---
Energy Booster 100 ¹⁴	---	---	---	0.87
Zinpro Availa Zn 120 ¹⁵	---	---	---	0.02
Vitamin Premix E, 2000 IU/lb	0.20	1.47	0.56	0.17
Trace-mineral-vitamin premix	0.26	0.29	0.18	0.26

¹Anionic mineral supplement (Dairy Nutrition Plus, Landus Cooperative, Des Moines, IA)

²Molasses-based liquid supplement (Quality Liquid Feeds, Dodgeville, WI)

³Ruminally protected soybean meal (Ag Processing Inc., Omaha, NE)

⁴Marine and animal RUP supplement (H. J. Baker & Bros. Inc., Westport, CT).

⁵Potassium carbonate (Arm & Hammer Animal Nutrition, Church & Dwight Co. Inc., Princeton, NY).

- ⁶Immune stimulant (Phibro Animal Health Corp., Teaneck, NJ).
- ⁷Monensin (Elanco, Greenfield, IN).
- ⁸Yeast culture (Phibro Animal Health Corp., Teaneck, NJ).
- ⁹Larvicide (Central Life Science, Schaumburg, IL)
- ¹⁰Yeast culture (Diamond V. Inc., Cedar Rapids, IA)
- ¹¹Encapsulated choline (Balchem Corp., Montvale, NJ)
- ¹²Encapsulated Methionine, Adisseo, Alpharetta, GA
- ¹³Calcium salts of fatty acids (Virtus Nutrition, Corcoran, CA)
- ¹⁴Hydrolyzed animal and vegetable fatty acid (Milk Specialties, Eden Prairie, MN)
- ¹⁵Amino Acids-Zinc complex (Zinpro Corp., Eden Prairie, MN)

Table S2. Nutrient contents of the experimental diets fed to cows during the late lactation (lactating diet), far-off period (far-off diet), close-up period (close-up diet) and early lactation (fresh diet), calculated based on Cornell Net Carbohydrate and Protein System 6.55.

of DM ¹	Lactating	Far-off	Close-up	Fresh
CP, %	16.99	14.57	12.42	17.17
SP ² , %	5.59	5.64	4.12	5.52
aNDFom ³ , %	34.46	49.66	42.54	31.85
ADF, %	20.30	30.13	26.52	18.56
Starch, %	20.65	15.89	18.64	21.53
Sugar, %	4.47	2.37	4.49	6.10
EE ⁴ , %	4.30	3.34	4.41	4.82
NFC ⁴ , %	35.73	25.13	31.47	37.85
Ash, %	8.87	7.30	9.16	8.31
NE _L , Mcal/kg	1.63	1.33	1.32	1.69

¹Calculated using Cornell Net Carbohydrate and Protein System 6.55.

²SP = Soluble protein

³aNDFom = NDF determined using amylase and corrected for ash

⁴EE = Ether extract

⁵NFC, % = 100 – (%NDF + %CP + %EE + %Ash)

Table S3. Gene names and symbols, accession numbers, sequences of primers of genes examined

Gene name	Gene symbol	Genebank accession#	Primer ¹	Sequence (5'-3')
Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	<i>GAPDH</i>	NM_001034034	F	TGATGGACCAAGAAAGATCCAGGG
			R	TAGGGATTGACCTCACTGGCCCTCTT
Tumor necrosis factor	<i>TNF</i>	NM_173966	F	ACACTCAGGTCCTCTTCTC
			R	GGTTGTCTTCCAGCTTCAC
Interleukin-1 β	<i>IL1B</i>	NM_174093	F	CAGGGATCCTATTCTCTCCA
			R	CGTCACTGTAGTAAGCCATC
Interleukin-10	<i>IL10</i>	NM_174088	F	CCTTGTCGGAAATGATCCAG
			R	GGCAGAAAGCGATGACAG
Transforming Growth Factor β 1	<i>TGFB1</i>	NM_001166068.1	F	ACCCGCAGAGAGGAAATAG
			R	GGTTCATGCCGTGAATGG
Transforming Growth Factor β 2	<i>TGFB2</i>	NM_001113252.1	F	GAGGAATACTACGCCAAGGAG
			R	GGAGACGTCAAATCGGACA
Transforming Growth Factor β 3	<i>TGFB3</i>	NM_001101183.1	F	ACGAAACCAACCTGTTCC
			R	CTTGGCTATGTGCTCACC
hepatocyte growth factor	<i>HGF</i>	NM_001031751.2	F	CCCTTCTCGAAACAAGGAC
			R	TCCTTCAGGCCCATATAACC
Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor A	<i>VEGFA</i>	NM_174216.2	F	GGCTGCTGTAATGACGAAAG
			R	TGCTGTAGGAAGCTCATCTC
Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor C	<i>VEGFC</i>	NM_174488.2	F	CTCCATGTGTGTCCGTCTA
			R	CTTGAGAGAGAGGCACTGTA
Insulin-like growth factor 1	<i>IGF1</i>	NM_001077828.1	F	GAGTTGGTGGATGCTCTC
			R	CTCATCCACGATTCCTGTC
Insulin-like growth factor 2	<i>IGF2</i>	NM_174087.3	F	GTGCTGCTATGCTGCTTAC
			R	GGCTGCGTCGGTTTATG
Insulin-like growth factor-binding protein-5	<i>IGFBP5</i>	NM_001105327.2	F	TACCTGCCCAACTGTGA

Prolactin receptor	<i>PRLR</i>	NM_174155.3	R	CAGCTTCATCCCGTACTTG
			F	GGAAGGAGAAACACTCATCC
			R	GAGGAACTGATTCCCATCTG
